

D5.3: Pilot Deployment, Test and Demonstration (first version)

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the initial deployment, testing, and demonstration of the RESCALE platform with pilot partners PST and CC. It details the integration process, challenges, and testing results in real-world environments. The findings will guide improvements and future iterations to ensure practical applicability and effectiveness in real-world use cases.

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List of Abbreviations

API Application Programming Interface. 21, 26, 29

BOM Bill of Materials. 23, 38

CD Continuous Development. 7, 23, 30, 40

CI Continuous Integration. 7, 10, 13–17, 20–23, 25, 30, 33, 40

CLI Command Line Interface. 23

DL Deep Learning. 11

DSCG Dynamic Supply Chain component Guarantee. 7, 13, 14, 20, 29, 31, 38

IoT Internet of Things. 13

JSON JavaScript Object Notation. 22

KPI Key Performance Indicator. 36

LLM Large Language Model. 17

ML Machine Learning. 11

REST Representational State Transfer. 21, 22, 26, 29

SaaS Software as a Service. 13

SBOM Software Bill of Materials. 7, 16, 17, 20, 23, 25–27, 38

SSCG Static Supply Chain component Guarantee. 4, 7, 14–16, 20, 24, 29, 33–35, 38

TBOM Trusted Bill of Materials. 13, 20, 29, 38

UI User Interface. 21

URL Uniform Resource Locator. 15, 21, 22, 33

YAML YAML Ain't Markup Language. 14

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the initial results of the deployment and testing for the two pilot use cases. It summarizes the outcomes of the similarly titled Task 5.2. Both pilots have been deployed using the RESCALE platform and the first phase of validation has occurred.

The deliverable aims to present two core directions in the implementations of the two pilot use cases. Firstly, it details how the deployment and integration of the pilot use cases and the RESCALE platform were conducted. The technical details of the integration steps are presented, including the connections that are made to platform components as part of the use cases' workflows. An initial and brief evaluation of the coverage of user requirements is also conducted, based on the plans defined in Work Package 2. Secondly, the initial validation of the platform is performed through the two pilot use cases. Testing procedures have been established and a first round of outcomes is detailed. The emphasis is on covering as much of the platform as possible. Thus, the pilot use cases have selected a small, but highly representative part of their applications and frameworks as the Device Under Test.

Finally, the deliverable includes a plan for the remainder of Task 5.2 and establishes a road map to the final version. Finally, efforts to create a deeper integration between the pilots and the platform, increasing the number of components utilized are described. The results of this second phase will be reported in M34.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope & Contribution

This deliverable presents the first outcomes of Task 5.2 - Pilots Use Cases Deployment, Testing, and Demonstration, roughly half a year after the task started (September 2024). It presents the initial results of the deployment and testing for the two pilot use cases, first described in Deliverable 2.1. The main contribution of the deliverable can be divided into two related parts.

The first part describes the technical details related to the deployment of the two pilot use cases. This includes a short introduction, followed by a list of the integration points with the RESCALE platform and the concrete steps taken so far within Task 5.2. Completed user interfaces are presented alongside details of CI/CD pipeline steps and examples for text-based inputs and outputs for the various steps of the use case workflow. On the project management side, the deliverable includes the challenges that have so far been identified and presents a brief, initial look at which user requirements have so far been met. The list of components each pilot use case covers so far can be used as a high-level assessment of the integration work's progress. A list of the next steps toward finishing the deployment of the use case applications is included.

The second part relates to the initial validation of the platform that is conducted through the pilot use cases. The deliverable includes a common testing procedure for both pilots that is composed of a list of steps that aim to cover as much of the services of the RESCALE platform as possible at this stage in their implementation. The initial outcomes are presented through a selection of screenshots that illustrate the user-facing elements of the platform, while the data model is illustrated through example SBOMs and SSCGs. The dynamic testing results reported in the DSCG are planned to be included in the next iteration of this deliverable (D5.4).

Finally, the deliverable includes a plan for the remainder of Task 5.3 and establishes a road map to the final version. It describes how the testing will be extended to cover more platform components and evaluate a more complex supply chain.

1.2 Methodology and Contribution to Project Objectives

The project adopts a two-phase approach regarding Task 5.2. In the first phase, as presented in this deliverable, the pilot use cases have deployed, within their own infrastructure and development CI/CD pipelines, a well-defined, representative segment of their applications using the RESCALE platform. By limiting the scope in this manner, more emphasis and scrutiny could be placed on the important integration details. At the same time, this approach allowed for a very wide coverage of platform components. The project chose this somewhat unusual approach to achieve two goals which are crucial at this stage in the project's lifecycle.

The first goal was to provide feedback to component developers through a technological deep-dive. This was then used as a first, mostly informal, validation method for the outcomes of Work Package 2, in particular the high level architecture specifications and the user-facing interfaces. This goal is directly related to Objective 5.2: *Deploy integrated solutions into the actual use case environments as specified in Task 2.1 and implement the pilot applications.*

The extensive range of covered components not only ensured that feedback was accessible to all partners, but it also assessed the integration level of the entire platform. Considering the significant number of components in relation to the relatively few that the use case applications interact with directly, tests could only be successful if these components were well integrated with one another as part of the Task 5.1 efforts. When viewed from a broader, project-level perspective, this approach is well-founded.

The second goal, established by the consortium at an early stage of the project, was for the two pilot use cases to take central roles in ensuring that relevant user requirements are defined and thus that the project's outcomes are good candidates for future exploitation. Furthermore, the use case applications themselves provide the test cases needed to validate the correct functioning of RESCALE. This is inline with Objective 5.3: *Test and demonstrate the real-world applications that use RESCALE solutions* and Objective 5.4: *Validate implemented solutions against requirements and evaluate results against ambitions and targets*.

Both goals serve the project-level Objective 4: *Demonstrate and validate the effectiveness and accuracy of the proposed solutions in two complementary use cases with the active engagement of several stakeholders accomplishing at the end of the project a TRL4 for the entire platform*.

In the second phase, the use case applications will be extended, covering a wider part of PST's and CC's software and hardware offering. As the development of more individual components is finalized and their integration into the RESCALE platform completed, more complex testing procedures will be established. The plan for this phase is outlined in this deliverable, with results reported in the upcoming second and final version of this deliverable (D5.4).

1.3 Relation to Work Packages, Deliverables, and Activities

The first phase of Task 5.2 - Pilots Use Cases Deployment, Testing, and Demonstration, as reported in this deliverable, was closely linked to the outcomes of Work Package 2. Efforts followed the plan described in Task 2.1: Pilots Use Cases Specifications which defined key user scenarios and validation objectives. Furthermore, testing sought to establish the correctness of the platform's overall architecture, as specified in Task 2.3: High Level Architecture Specification which defined the high-level architectural interactions essential for ensuring correct integration.

Both pilot use cases strive to utilize as many of the platform components as possible, particularly those from the Assessment and Management domains with a focus on the Static Code Analysis Module. This included the outcomes of WP3: Static and Dynamic Analysis Testing, which included components directly used to assess the security aspects of the applications, as well as the outcomes of WP4: Trusted Supply Chain Establishment, which included the components that manage the platform-wide workflows. The integration work was performed as part of T5.1: Trust Orchestrator and Integration of RESCALE Solutions.

The following phase of Task 5.2 will be done in close cooperation with Task 5.3: Continuous Validation and Evaluation to ensure that testing procedures are sufficient in their completeness to validate the achievement of the previously established requirements. This will be achieved through joint integration meetings, regular feedback loops, and combined testing activities. These efforts will be reported in Deliverable 5.4 in M34.

1.4 Intended Audience

This document is publicly available and should be of use to anyone interested in the detailed description of the deployment and testing of the two pilot use cases of the RESCALE project.

1.5 Document Structure

Section 1 serves as an introduction to the document. It provides information about the document's purpose, including its role in the RESCALE project, the methodology with which its contents were created, its structure and the audience to which it is mainly addressed.

Section 2 is dedicated to providing a high-level overview of the RESCALE platform's architecture, as defined in Task 2.3. Section 3 is dedicated to the first pilot use case: Auto-Placement Security Aware Augmented Data-Flow and Infrastructure. It describes how the use case applications interact and integrate with the platform components. Beyond the technical descriptions, a subsection is dedicated to providing an initial evaluation of progress in terms of meeting user requirements and assessing the coverage of platform components. The list of the following integration and development steps is also outlined. Section 4 is dedicated to RESCALE's second pilot use case: Privacy-by-Design Distributed Cloud and Edge Storage and matches the structure of the previous section.

Section 5 describes the test procedure steps that pilot partners took to evaluate and validate the effectiveness of the RESCALE solution. Section 6 provides a roadmap, from the perspective of the two pilot use cases, on the planned evolution of the RESCALE platform and the role the two use case partners have in this process. Finally, Section 7 summarizes the contents of the deliverable and provides a brief description of its role in the life-cycle of the project.

2 Architecture Overview

Figure 1, depicts the high-level architecture of the RESCALE platform as outlined in D2.3. With respect to the pilot partners CC and PST, the static code analysis module as well as the dynamic testing module, e.g. the “Assessment Domain”, have a significant role since both partners need to integrate the respective modules of that domain into their CI system for automation purposes. The “Management Domain” as well as “Security and Trust Domain” are accessible for the pilot partners by means of a cloud service and hence a local partner specific setup is not necessary, even though it is technically possible.

Figure 1: RESCALE High-Level Architecture

For both pilot partners the “Management Domain” and “Security and Trust Domain” are considered opaque. They are accessed through APIs from the “Assessment Domain” and through a graphical “Dashboard” but don’t require further technical knowledge to make use of them, beside these interfaces. More precisely, the “Static Code Analysis Module” as well as the “Dynamic Testing Module”, which are packaged using container technologies, just need to be configured accordingly by the pilot partners. In that sense, as it will be outlined in sections

3 and 4, for adopters of RESCALE these modules are a plug-and-play solution, given certain infrastructure requirements to run them.

Figure 1 serves as a visual guide for sections 3 and 4 to describe which components of the overall RESCALE platform are utilized in the integration efforts of both pilot partners.

Furthermore, the pilot partners utilize ML/DL enhanced static and dynamic analysis tooling developed within WP3 activities. Not all tools are available yet for the pilots, most of these tools are currently in the process of being embedded into the respective static code analysis module or dynamic testing module (as part of WP3 activities, see figure 1). All of these tools were presented in the recent deliverables D3.1, D3.3, D3.5 and D3.7. So far the tools SAVE-ME and SASTer are completely integrated by the pilots, the other tools are supposed to be integrated within the next two months. The tables 1 and 2 provide an overview of all tools, for static and dynamic testing, and the pilots partners intention of usage.

Table 1: Overview Static Analysis Tooling, Intention of Usage

Tool	Description	PST	CC
SASTer	Tool bundle for different programming languages (so far Python, C, C++)		X
SAVE-ME	Erlang specific code analysis	X	
IVEE	Intelligent Vulnerability Exposure Engine, based on symbolic execution techniques		X
DetectEr	Formal Verification for Erlang using Hennessy–Milner Logic	X	

Table 2: Overview Dynamic Analysis Tooling, Intention of Usage

Tool	Description	PST	CC
RAISE	REST API fuzzer working on OpenAPI specifications	X	X
EvoMaster	Integrated fuzzing tool for security testing on RESTful APIs	X	X
FATex	Analysis for firmware of embedded systems	X	
InSpectre Gadget	Detection and analysis of Spectre-type (hardware) vulnerabilities		X
SafeFetch	Detection and mitigation of double-fetch (software) vulnerabilities		X
Dynamic Hardware Analyzer	Side Channel Attack Assessment	X	

Please note that these tables of intention are subject to change as the tools are still under development, and it is sometimes very hard to predict the effort required to integrate these tools for

meaningful usage. As mentioned before, only a small part (SAVE-ME and SASTer) of these tools is currently actually integrated and used by the pilots.

3 Deployment of the RESCALE platform for GRiSP.io

3.1 Description

The Peer Stritzinger GmbH (PST) use case within the RESCALE project is dedicated to strengthening security in distributed computing environments. Initially outlined in Deliverable D2.1 – Use Case Specification (First Version), the use case has been progressively refined in alignment with the development of the RESCALE platform. In the following, the use case will be outlined again, reflecting its current state.

PST is developing [GRiSP.io](#) [8], a SaaS platform designed for the secure and efficient orchestration of distributed applications across cloud, edge, and IoT devices. GRiSP.io is designed to work with the GRiSP2 [7] board. The software stack of GRiSP.io and GRiSP is built on Erlang [6], with additional C components used for interfacing with specific hardware. Aside from manufacturing-related software components, all software related to GRiSP2 is open-source.

RESCALE enhances this use case by allowing to automate security assessments of components, ensuring early detection of vulnerabilities, particularly in third-party (external) elements. A key enabler of this security automation is the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM), which serves as a fundamental component for securing the software supply chain.

PST is also actively involved in railway systems, particularly in digital display systems, where the hardware closely resembles the GRiSP2 board. Although this use case is largely limited to closed-source components, there is potential for PST to leverage RESCALE's security assessment capabilities in this domain.

PST started the integration of RESCALE into the GRiSP.io software project, hosted on GitHub. The rest of the section is dedicated to details of this integration. It should be noted that PST is keen to integrate RESCALE with other software projects and might even provide an interface in GRiSP.io for customers. In this sense, an integration with GRiSP.io is a blueprint for other PST projects as those are all related to similar (Erlang-based) technologies.

3.2 Integration steps

As many other CI systems, GitHub CI is usable as part of a hosted software project, and in particular, the behavior of the CI can be configured using text files that are part of the versioned source code. These text files define CI pipelines and their respective sequence of jobs together with dependencies between them and other configuration parameters. Such jobs then get executed using so-called CI runners, e.g. hosts that are linked to the CI system, which usually (but not always) use Docker as a technological foundation to run these jobs in an isolated manner. The information on which Docker image to use for which job is also part of the mentioned text file. This basic concept is visualized in Figure 2.

Currently, the static code analysis module is implemented as a single container while the dynamic testing module is a set of different containers for each tool plus an additional container which runs the DSCG Generator based on output from the tool containers. The reader is referenced to Deliverables D3.1 and D3.2 for further details. The task of integrating RESCALE

Figure 2: GitHub CI Conceptual View

into the CI system of GRiSP.io can hence be boiled down to the integration of the Docker containers. While the pipeline for the static code analysis module can be modeled as a single job, the pipeline for the dynamic analysis will be more complicated as output from tool containers needs to be ingested into, e.g. the DSCG Generator container.

GitHub CI Script - Static Code Analysis Module

PST has so far integrated the static code analysis module into the GRiSP.io GitHub CI system. Integration involved creating a configuration file that defines the execution logic and workflow of the CI system. In the case of GitHub CI, this configuration file is formatted as YAML, and it describes pipelines (also called workflows) and their respective jobs. Typically, there can be multiple such files for different purposes, they just need to be present under the project folder `.github/workflows/` so the CI system knows how to find the configuration files. For the static code analysis module, there is just one configuration file, for the dynamic analysis module, another file will be added in the near future.

The CI script for the static code analysis will be explained piece by piece in the following:

```

name: Run static analysis module

on:
  workflow_dispatch:

jobs:
  generate-sscg:
    runs-on: ubuntu-latest
  
```

This piece of configuration defines the name of the CI pipeline (“Run static analysis module”). Further, this pipeline is configured to be executed by a manual trigger through the `on` statement. It is also possible to trigger the pipeline automatically on every change of the repository code, leading to a new SSCG version for every committed change. However, since currently many people are working actively on the platform it is desirable to manually start the pipeline given some coordination with other partners.

The third part of the code above starts to define the actual jobs which are executed in the pipeline. For the static code analysis module there is just one job necessary (`generate-sscg`), which will execute the tests, generate the SSCG and optionally publish it to the RESCALE platform. The whole job is executed on a virtual machine running `ubuntu-latest`, e.g. the latest iteration of the Ubuntu Linux distribution. This virtual machine is also capable of running Docker containers.

```

steps:
  - name: Set up SSH key
    uses: webfactory/ssh-agent@v0.9.0
    with:
      ssh-private-key: ${ secrets.STRITZINGER_BOT_SSH_KEY }

  - name: Check out repository
    uses: actions/checkout@v4
    with:
      show-progress: false
      path: repo

  - name: Make output directory
    run: mkdir out/

```

The above configuration represents the first number of steps that the `generate-sscg` job is going to execute. First a SSH key is set up based on the CI secrets management. This key is necessary for accessing the GRiSP.io repository. Then the GRiSP.io repository is checked out into the Ubuntu virtual machine and an output directory for the SSCG is prepared.

```

- name: Run static analysis container
  uses: addnab/docker-run-action@v3
  with:
    username: ${ secrets.RESCALE_HARBOR_USERNAME }
    password: ${ secrets.RESCALE_HARBOR_PASSWORD }
    registry: harbor.rescale-project.eu
    image:
      harbor.rescale-project.eu/wp3/static_analysis_module:latest
    shell: bash
    options: |
      -v ${ github.workspace }/repo:/user_files/
      -v ${ github.workspace }/out:/app/out/
      -e USER_ACCESS_TOKEN=${ secrets.RESCALE_ACCESS_TOKEN }
      -e LANG_INFO=Erlang
      -e SRC_PATH=/user_files/src/
      -e SBOM_PATH=/user_files/sbom.json
      -e DRY_RUN=false
    run: /usr/local/bin/scam-engine.sh

```

The above step “Run static analysis container” is the core part of the whole CI pipeline for the static code analysis. The URL

```
harbor.rescale-project.eu/wp3/static_analysis_module:latest
```

declares that the latest iteration of the static code analysis module Docker container should be fetched from the `harbour.rescale-project.eu` Docker registry, which was specifically

setup for the RESCALE project. Since this is a private registry there is a need for authentication which is given through the username and password sections.

The Docker container is started with a bash shell, which allows the execution of shell commands using the run section. The command `/usr/local/bin/scam-engine.sh` executes the SCAM engine (see D3.1), which orchestrates the execution of static code analysis tooling inside the container based on content in options.

Using the `-v` option it is possible to map volumes (e.g. folders) from the Ubuntu virtual machine inside the Docker container such that the previously checked-out repository as well as the output folder, is available from within the container. Further, using the `-e` option it is possible to define environment variables to be honored inside the container (see D3.1). The `USER_ACCESS_TOKEN` allows for authenticated and authorized communication of the SSCG Generator with the RESCALE platform. The `LANG_INFO` defines the involved programming language technologies, which could also be a list of multiple different technologies. Further the `SRC_PATH` and `SBOM_PATH` point to the source code to be analyzed as well as the respective SBOM which is expected to be pre-generated and present in the repository. Finally the `DRY_RUN` variable allows to execute the module without publishing data (e.g. for test runs) to the RESCALE platform, if set to `true`.

To augment the `DRY_RUN` functionality, there is a last step in the CI script:

```
- name: Archive SSCG
  uses: actions/upload-artifact@v4
  if: ${{ always() }}
  with:
    name: SSCG
    path: ./out/sscg.json
    if-no-files-found: error
    compression-level: 9
```

In any case, the SSCG will be stored locally as a CI artifact for introspection and an error will be generated, leading the pipeline to fail if the SSCG can't be found. This allows developers to inspect the final result of the pipeline, and also this adds a plausibility check if everything worked fine.

Files used or generated by the PST GitHub CI system can be inspected at the [RESCALE SharePoint \[13\]](#).

GitHub CI UI View

It is possible to control and introspect the CI jobs in GitHub CI using a web interface. Figure 3 showcases an overview of several executed pipeline runs for the static code analysis module which happened throughout the integration activities. On the top right, there is a button to manually trigger the execution of such a pipeline based on a branch. As mentioned earlier, the CI configuration is part of the versioned source code, and therefore, the CI activities are always specific to Git branches. This is the reason why next to the Git commit message on the left, there is also the branch name in the center.

It is also possible to further introspect each job of an executed pipeline as illustrated by Figure 4. Each step of a job can be expanded to see step specific logs. This, in particular, allows to

Run static analysis module Filter workflow runs

[sscg.yaml](#)

6 workflow runs		Event	Status	Branch	Actor
This workflow has a <code>workflow_dispatch</code> event trigger. Run workflow					
✓	Always try to archive SSCG, even on a failure Run static analysis module #19: Commit 13a381e pushed by matlaj	matlaj/sscg_dry_off		yesterday	3m 41s
✗	Always try to archive SSCG, even on a failure Run static analysis module #18: Commit 56bdd84 pushed by matlaj	matlaj/sscg_dry_off		2 days ago	3m 45s
✗	SSCG: Turn off dry run mode Run static analysis module #17: Commit 635a5df pushed by matlaj	matlaj/sscg_dry_off		2 days ago	2m 43s
✓	Run static analysis module Run static analysis module #16: Manually run by matlaj	main		last week	2m 36s
✓	Run static analysis module in the CI Run static analysis module #15: Commit cf9f1ed pushed by matlaj	matlaj/sscg		last week	2m 52s
✓	Run static analysis module in the CI Run static analysis module #14: Commit c63354c pushed by matlaj	matlaj/sscg		last week	3m 16s

Figure 3: GitHub CI UI Pipeline View

introspect logs from the actual run of the static code analysis module, which are showcased in Section 5.2. It can also be seen that a run of the actual static code analysis container takes a bit more than 3 minutes.

3.3 Challenges and Solutions

There have not been any major problems or challenges in integrating the static code analysis module. However, the module has been developed to a large part by PST with its own CI requirements in mind, and hence, it is not surprising that it could be integrated into PST's own CI system with ease. It must be noted though that a rather powerful CI host is recommended to handle the workloads of local LLM models (which are utilized e.g. by SAVE-ME).

However, there was a significant challenge in generating the actual SBOM for GRiSP.io (see [RESCALE SharePoint](#) [13]) as the current state of tooling in Erlang certainly does not meet modern requirements. Although there exists a plugin called `rebar3_sbom` [12] for the Erlang build tool `rebar3` [10], the resulting SBOM is outdated and impractical, as it outputs CycloneDX [2] 1.1. To address this, PST submitted a pull request on GitHub [11] to improve the tool. However, the maintainer expressed a preference for a broader redesign and refactoring of the `rebar3_sbom` plugin. This sparked further discussions about CycloneDX support in Erlang: Depending on how the RESCALE project as a whole evolves in the future, PST might invest into the development of a standalone CycloneDX support library for Erlang, which could then be integrated by the `rebar3_sbom` plugin as well. For now, PST is using their own fork of `rebar3_sbom`, incorporating the improvements proposed in their pull request.

```

generate-sscg
succeeded 3 hours ago in 3m 29s

> ✓ Set up job 1s
> ✓ Build addnab/docker-run-action@v3 4s
v ✓ Set up SSH key 0s
  1 ▶ Run webfactory/ssh-agent@v0.9.0
  6 Starting ssh-agent
  7 SSH_AUTH_SOCK=/tmp/ssh-2Ir6L28kt9c0/agent.1875
  8 SSH_AGENT_PID=1876
  9 Adding private key(s) to agent
 10 Identity added: (stdin) ((stdin))
 11 Key(s) added:
 12 256 SHA256:V9+YExeyhX5H9uG7h+43SD87SInEJL09P10khF7Pi4U (stdin) (ED25519)
 13 Configuring deployment key(s)
 14 Comment for (public) key 'ssh-ed25519 AAAAC3NzaC1lZDI1NTE5AAAAIG7k6q2Wrgk9i0vffiBE4hVtsRfdpwL2ewlIMrZiuBX4
    (stdin)' does not match GitHub URL pattern. Not treating it as a GitHub deploy key.

> ✓ Check out repository 0s
> ✓ Set up Erlang 6s
> ✓ Make output directory 0s
> ✓ Run static analysis container 3m 15s
> ✓ Archive SSCG 1s
> ✓ Post Check out repository 0s
> ✓ Post Set up SSH key 0s
> ✓ Complete job 0s

```

Figure 4: GitHub CI UI Job View

3.4 User requirements covered

Table 3 illustrates which user requirements of RESCALE based on D2.3 are covered from the view of PST. Note that there are several user requirements which are not directly related to the first step of integration as outlined in this document.

Table 3: List of Initial User Requirements for RESCALE

URID	Title	Comment
UR010	Static Code Analysis of Erlang	SAVE-ME is integrated into the static code analysis module and usable, though the tool is in an early stage and requires a lot more development work
UR011	Static Code Analysis of GRiSP.io IoT Platform	The module is integrated and able to push SSCGs into the RESCALE platform

Table 3 – continued from previous page

URID	Title	Comment
UR012	Dynamic Security Testing of GRiSP.io IoT Platform	The module is ready to be integrated in the very near future, including API fuzzing tools like RAISE and Evomaster which can be used in combination with OpenAPI
UR013	Continuous Security Testing for GRiSP.io IoT Platform	Partially covered by means of the static code analysis module
UR014	Dry/Standalone Testing for GRiSP.io IoT Platform	Integrated for the static code analysis module
UR015	Dry/Standalone Testing for GRiSP.io IoT Platform Users	Not implemented yet
UR016	Constructive Feedback on Security Findings for GRiSP.io IoT Platform	Not implemented yet, requires more research and implementation within the SSCG/DSCG Generators as well as the other RESCALE components
UR017	Constructive Feedback on Security Findings for GRiSP.io Users	See UR016
UR018	Quick to Understand Summaries of Security Findings for Executive Entities	See UR016
UR019	Dynamic Mutation Fuzzing Integration into GRiSP.io	Not implemented yet, possibly covered in future phases of the project (this is a 'could' requirement)
UR020	TBOM for GRiSP.io IoT Platform	Not integrated yet, though a concrete plan forward is laid out for that in Section 3.6
UR021	TBOM Integration into GRiSP.io IoT Platform	See UR020
UR022	User Specified Trust Zones in GRiSP.io	This is a feature specific to PST which is currently under development. The feature partially relies on data sensitivity information from the RESCALE platform, which might be subject to future project efforts. (This is a 'should' requirement)
UR023	Cryptographic Primitive Assignment in GRiSP.io	See UR022
UR024	Sensitive Data Classification in GRiSP.io IoT Platform	See UR022
UR025	Explore Erlang VM Separation for GRiSP.io IoT Platform	Not implemented yet, possibly covered in future phases of the project (this is a 'could' requirement)
UR026	Low-Level System Security Testing of GRiSP.io IoT Platform	Not implemented yet, possibly covered in future phases of the project (this is a 'should' requirement)

Figure 5: GRI SP.io Component in the RESCALE Dashboard

3.5 Components covered

The current state of the integration includes the static code analysis module and in particular, the tool SAVE-ME (see D3.1) which is a static code analysis tool for the Erlang programming language.

With respect to the architecture overview (Figure 1), it is currently possible for PST to use the services of the “Management Domain” with a limited set of features. It is possible to create a new component, which yields a `RESCALE_ACCESS_TOKEN` that can be used by PST’s CI system to push SBOM, SSCG and DSCG information. These informations are reflected in the RESCALE Dashboard as showcased by Figure 5. So far only the static code analysis module is integrated, and hence just an SSCG can be pushed. Note that GRI SP.io is just a product name, the PST internal technical name for the GRI SP.io project is “Seawater” which is the reason why that name is used in the RESCALE Dashboard.

The “Security and Trust Domain” (see Figure 1) is, as of now, only partially integrated. The document repositories for SSCG, DSCG, and TBOM are functional, even though just the SSCG repository is used right now. More details can be found in D5.1.

3.6 Next steps

The integration of the dynamic testing module will be the next prioritized step. However, the dynamic testing module is far more complex and uses an ensemble of Docker containers. The general approach here is to execute all tool specific containers and cache the output (e.g. the test reports) in the CI system such that in a final step, a container with the DSCG Generator can use these test reports together with further options to generate and publish the DSCG.

Figure 6 captures this idea. Two stages are used where the first stage runs a tool container as a single job, possibly in parallel as the single tool containers are independent from each other. Then, the outputs from each tool are aggregated in a cache which is provided by GitHub CI.

Figure 6: Conceptual Dynamic Analysis CI Integration

It is usually not necessary to define the cache itself in the CI configuration; it is rather set up automatically by defining dependencies between jobs in a way that requires a forwarding of artefacts from one job to another.

For dynamic testing, the tools RAISE and Evomaster (see D3.3) are of particular interest as they are API fuzzing tools working on OpenAPI [9] specifications, which are already integrated for GRiSP.io. Hence an integration with these tools in the PST CI system should be relatively straightforward. The integration with FATex needs more research, as the overall setup involves very hardware specific configuration.

As PST might also provide access to the RESCALE platform and the analysis tooling through a web UI there is a need to execute standalone workloads triggered through that web UI. This can also be realized using GitHub CI with pipelines (or workflows) that are triggered by means of a REST interface. A customer would provide a URL to its (usually also GitHub hosted) software project which is supposed to be tested.

```
name: API-Triggered Job
```

```
on:
```

```
  repository_dispatch:
    types: [trigger-ci]
```

```
jobs:
```

```
  api-job:
```

```
runs-on: ubuntu-latest
steps:
  - run: echo "Triggered by API!"
  - run: echo "URL: ${github.event.client_payload.url}"
```

In the above example, such a GitHub CI workflow is defined. For demonstration purposes, there is just one job `api-job` that is triggered through a REST interface. The job simply returns a URL that was provided by the customer. The complete CI workflow can be extended in a very similar way as presented with GRiSP.io and the static code analysis module. The only difference here is that the software project to be tested is fetched from a configurable source.

The whole workflow can then be triggered using e.g. the following skeleton of a cURL call:

```
curl -X POST -H "Accept: application/vnd.github.everest-preview+json" \
-H "Authorization: token YOUR_GITHUB_TOKEN" \
https://api.github.com/repos/OWNER/REPO/dispatches \
-d '{
  "event_type": "trigger-ci",
  "client_payload": {
    "url": "https://github.com/some/project"
  }
}'
```

Note that the customer provided URL is placed in the `client_payload` JSON object and the specific CI workflow is identified using the `event_type` key. This actual integration will certainly vary in the details from this approach.

4 Deployment of the RESCALE platform for SkyFlok

4.1 Description

SkyFlok is Chocolate Cloud's main product aimed at individuals and small to medium businesses. It is a secure file storage platform which enables users to store their data easily and reliably across multiple cloud storage providers (see D2.1 for more details). Static and dynamic testing of the SkyFlok components play a key role in making sure the solution is secure and free of vulnerabilities. Chocolate Cloud stores the source code of its software components in Bitbucket [1] and uses Bitbucket Pipelines for CI/CD tasks, therefore running the RESCALE testing modules will be demonstrated using this tool. The following two subsections describe the integrations steps the pilot took through two separate software components to maximize the coverage of the RESCALE tools.

4.2 Static and dynamic testing of rlnclib

4.2.1 Description

Rlnclib is Chocolate Cloud's Random Linear Network Coding library written in C++ used to encode and decode file fragments when uploading or downloading files to its SkyFlok platform. It uses cmake as a build system. It plays an important role in the pilot's software architecture, because many other components build upon this library's features, so it is crucial to test it thoroughly.

4.2.2 Integration steps

To generate an SBOM for rlnclib pilot partner CC uses cdxgen, which is the official CyclonDX CLI tool to generate BOM files [3]. This tool can be run in a docker container and it produces an sbom.json file by analyzing the CMakeLists.txt of the project (see [RESCALE SharePoint \[13\]](#)).

Running the Static Code Analysis Module locally with DRY_RUN

Below is a batch script that runs the static analyzer module locally with DRY_RUN enabled.

```
docker run -e DRY_RUN=true ^
-e SBOM_PATH="/app/sbom.json" -v .\bom.json:/app/sbom.json ^
-e SRC_PATH="/app/src/" -v .\rlnclib:/app/src -v /app/src/build -v
  /app/src/extern ^
-e LANG_INFO="Cpp" ^
-v .\out:/app/out ^
harbor.rescale-project.eu/wp3/static_analysis_module
```

This docker run command uses volumes to mount the sbom.json, and the source code to be used by the static analyzer module. Paths and other configuration parameters are passed as environment variables. For the output it also utilizes a volume. Successfully executing the command produces the following output.

```
Validating sbom.json...
BOM validated successfully.
[C++] Processing C++ source at /app/src/ with output at
/app/out/test-reports/
[SASter] Running scan...
[SASter] Scan completed
[C++] C++ source scans completed
[SSCG Generator] Generating SSCG...
- SBOM Path: /app/sbom.json
- Test Report Folder: /app/out/test-reports/
- SSCG Path: /app/out/sscg.json
JSON successfully stored to /app/out/sscg.json

Validating sscg.json...
BOM validated successfully.
Dry run mode enabled. SSCG is not published.
SSCG generation/publishing process completed
```

In the logs we can see the static analysis module ran SASter (see Table 1), then generated an SSCG. After that, it validated the sscg and finally, because it is a dry run, the uploading of the SSCG is skipped. The output is saved to the out folder as sscg.json, so the developers can analyze the results.

Running the Static Code Analysis Module in CI with DRY_RUN

Below you can find the excerpt from the bitbucket-pipelines.yml for running RESCALE static analysis module in Bitbucket Pipelines.

```
- step: &rescale-static-analysis
  name: Rescale Static Analysis test
  services:
    - docker
  script:
    - docker run -v $BITBUCKET_CLONE_DIR:/app:rw -t
      ghcr.io/cyclonedx/cdxgen -r /app -o /app/sbom.json -t cpp
    - docker login harbor.rescale-project.eu --username
      $RESCALE_HARBOR_USERNAME --password $RESCALE_HARBOR_PASSWORD
    - >
      docker run
      -e DRY_RUN=true
      -e SBOM_PATH="/app/sbom.json" -v
        $BITBUCKET_CLONE_DIR/sbom.json:/app/sbom.json
      -e SRC_PATH="/app/src/" -v $BITBUCKET_CLONE_DIR:/app/src
      -v $BITBUCKET_CLONE_DIR/out:/app/out
      -e LANG_INFO="Cpp"
      harbor.rescale-project.eu/wp3/static_analysis_module
  artifacts: # Store build artifacts for use in the following steps
    - out/sscg.json
    - out/test-reports/*
```

First, the script runs `cdxgen` to generate an SBOM, then logs in to harbor to be able to pull images, and finally runs the static analysis docker container, by mounting volumes and passing options using environment variables. As a post step, the `ssc.json` and the test reports are uploaded as artifacts. Storing these artifacts enables the developers to download and analyze the results and fix the findings before releasing the software.

Figure 7: Running the static analyzer in Bitbucket Pipelines

Running the Static Code Analysis Module in CI without `DRY_RUN`

The step to run the static analyzer without `DRY_RUN` differs only in the configuration parameters of the `docker run` command.

```
- step: &rescale-static-analysis
  name: Rescale Static Analysis test
  services:
    - docker
  script:
    - docker run -v $BITBUCKET_CLONE_DIR:/app:rw -t
      ghcr.io/cyclonedx/cdxgen -r /app -o /app/sbom.json -t cpp
    - docker login harbor.rescale-project.eu --username
      $RESCALE_HARBOR_USERNAME --password $RESCALE_HARBOR_PASSWORD
    - >
      docker run
      -e SBOM_PATH="/app/sbom.json" -v
        $BITBUCKET_CLONE_DIR/sbom.json:/app/sbom.json
      -e SRC_PATH="/app/src/" -v $BITBUCKET_CLONE_DIR:/app/src
      -v $BITBUCKET_CLONE_DIR/out:/app/out
      -e USER_ACCESS_TOKEN=$RESCALE_ACCESS_TOKEN
      -e LANG_INFO="Cpp"
      harbor.rescale-project.eu/wp3/static_analysis_module
  artifacts: # Store build artifacts for use in the following steps
    - out/sscg.json
    - out/test-reports/*
```

First the `DRY_RUN` parameter is omitted, and an access token is passed. This access token is generated through the RESCALE Dashboard.

4.2.3 Challenges and Solutions

One challenge the pilot partner CC encountered during the integration of the RESCALE platform was to find an SBOM generator for C++ projects. There are a few, which are paid, so not viable for the pilot. A free, open-source alternative is the `cdxgen`, but due to a bug in the library, it was not able to process the `CMakeLists.txt` files of `rlnclib`. Luckily, with the help of the maintainer, the developers from the pilot were able to find and fix the bug and submit a pull request (see [pull request](#))

Another challenge was to find the correct commands and parameters to invoke the analyzer modules. It had to be gathered from multiple sources, code repositories and partners. A single source of truth, for example, a section on the Dashboard on how to run the static and dynamic analyzers, would help a lot and speed up the integration process.

4.2.4 Next steps

The dynamic testing module is not integrated yet. This part will be integrated in the following period and showcased in the second version of this deliverable (D5.4). Running the dynamic module involves more complex steps as it uses a multi-docker container setup. Below is a pseudo-code describing the steps.

```
- get sscg serial id from the RESCALE backend using curl
- docker run dynamic_testing_module_for_cpp
  # pass the built binary of rlnclib
- docker run dscg_generator
  # pass the results from the previous step and the sscg serial id
```

4.3 Static and dynamic testing of a SkyFlok microservice

4.3.1 Description

Chocolate Cloud's SkyFlok platform is built on a microservice architecture, the components include authentication, user, storage backend, file, email, etc. services. These are all written in python using Flask or FastAPI libraries to provide a REST API.

4.3.2 Integration steps

The pilot partner CC used `cyclonedx-bom` python package to generate an SBOM for the microservice written in python. Its supported data sources are `virtualenv`, `poetry`, `pipenv`, `pip's requirements.txt`, etc. CC already uses `requirements.txt` to manage its dependencies so it was easy to integrate this tool. To correctly extract the project name and version, a `pyproject.toml` file had to be created and filled with information. On success the tool produces an `sbom.json` (see [RESCALE SharePoint \[13\]](#)).

Running the Static Code Analysis Module locally with DRY_RUN

A windows batch script to run the static analyzer can be seen below.

```
docker run -e DRY_RUN=true ^
  -e SBOM_PATH="/app/sbom.json" -v .\sbom.json:/app/sbom.json ^
  -e SRC_PATH="/app/src/" -v ./:/app/src -v /app/src/.venv ^
  -e LANG_INFO="Python" ^
  -v .\out:/app/out ^
  harbor.rescale-project.eu/wp3/static_analysis_module
```

The SBOM and the source code is provided using volumes. The .venv folder is skipped intentionally to omit it from being analyzed. Using LANG_INFO environment variable the python tools are selected to be run. The static analyzer saves the output to the out folder.

Running the Static Code Analysis Module in CI with DRY_RUN

The snippet below shows how to run the static analyzer in Bitbucket Pipelines with DRY_RUN.

```
- step:
  name: Rescale Static Analysis test
  services:
    - docker
  caches:
    - docker
  script:
    - pip install cyclonedx-bom
    - cyclonedx-py requirements --pyproject pyproject.toml --sv 1.6 -o
      sbom.json
    - docker login harbor.rescale-project.eu --username
      $RESCALE_HARBOR_USERNAME --password $RESCALE_HARBOR_PASSWORD
    - >
      docker run
      -e DRY_RUN=true
      -e SBOM_PATH="/app/sbom.json" -v
        $BITBUCKET_CLONE_DIR/sbom.json:/app/sbom.json
      -e SRC_PATH="/app/src/" -v $BITBUCKET_CLONE_DIR:/app/src
      -v $BITBUCKET_CLONE_DIR/out:/app/out
      -e LANG_INFO="Python"
      harbor.rescale-project.eu/wp3/static_analysis_module
  artifacts: # Store build artifacts for use in the following steps
    - out/sscg.json
    - out/test-reports/*
```

First the script installs cyclonedx-bom, then runs the tool to generate an sbom.json. The next lines log in to harbor, and finally run the harbor.rescale-project.eu/wp3/static_analysis_module image. This docker command uses volumes and environment variables to pass files and configuration parameters.

Running the Static Code Analysis Module in CI without DRY_RUN

The snippet below differs from the previous one only in the passed parameters. DRY_RUN is skipped, and a token is passed, which is stored in Bitbucket Pipelines variables as a secret.

```
- step:
  name: Rescale Static Analysis test
  services:
    - docker
  caches:
    - docker
  script:
    - pip install cyclonedx-bom
    - cyclonedx-py requirements --pyproject pyproject.toml --sv 1.6 -o
      sbom.json
    - docker login harbor.rescale-project.eu --username
      $RESCALE_HARBOR_USERNAME --password $RESCALE_HARBOR_PASSWORD
    - >
      docker run
      -e SBOM_PATH="/app/sbom.json" -v
        $BITBUCKET_CLONE_DIR/sbom.json:/app/sbom.json
      -e SRC_PATH="/app/src/" -v $BITBUCKET_CLONE_DIR:/app/src
      -v $BITBUCKET_CLONE_DIR/out:/app/out
      -e USER_ACCESS_TOKEN=$RESCALE_ACCESS_TOKEN
      -e LANG_INFO="Python"
      harbor.rescale-project.eu/wp3/static_analysis_module
  artifacts: # Store build artifacts for use in the following steps
    - sbom.json
    - out/sscg.json
    - out/test-reports/*
```

When the above snippet is run, the progress and the result can be checked in the Bitbucket Pipelines (see 8).

Figure 8: Running the RESCALE Static Analysis Module in Bitbucket Pipelines

4.3.3 Challenges and Solutions

No new challenges have been identified in this integration step.

4.3.4 Next steps

As with 4.2.4 the dynamic testing module is next to be integrated into this use case. The two REST API tester tools (RAISE and EVOmaster) are planned to be used for this scenario. These consume the OpenAPI specification of a webservice. Below is a pseudo-code describing the planned steps to run the dynamic testing.

```
- get sscg serial id from the RESCALE backend using curl
- docker run skyflok-microservice
- docker run dynamic_testing_module_raise # pass the openapi
  specification url
- docker run dynamic_testing_module_evomaster # pass the openapi
  specification url
- docker run dscg_generator # pass the results from the previous step
  and the sscg serial id
```

After the DSCG will be submitted to the platform a TBOM should be generated and stored on the blockchain. The resulting TBOM should be visible in the dashboard, and the pilot should be notified when new supply chain vulnerabilities are found for this specific component. Furthermore, pilot partner CC intends to leverage the tools provided by the RESCALE solution for more of its microservices, ensuring broad coverage of software components. Additionally, there are plans to extend this approach to CC's internal software supply chain.

4.4 Components covered

In the current state of the project the **Static Code Analysis Module** is integrated into pilot partner CC's pipeline. For the two scenarios, the **SASter** tool is started in the **Static Code Analyzer** in both C++ and Python mode. The **SSCG Generator** is used to generate the SSCG and upload it to the RESCALE backend, the **Management Module** in particular. During the integration effort the **Dashboard** was used extensively. Other components of the Management and Security & Trust Domain (see Figure 1) were used only indirectly. Later in the project the **Dynamic Testing Module** will be integrated and tools like **EvoMaster**, **RAISE**, etc. will be used to run dynamic tests. In the end a TBOM should be created and stored using the **Trust Storage**.

4.5 User requirements covered

Table 4 shows which user requirements of pilot partner CC are covered. See D2.3 for a full list and description of these user requirements.

Table 4: List of Initial User Requirements for RESCALE

URID	Title	Comment
UR001	Static code security testing of SkyFlok	Static code analysis is available for both c++ and python.

Table 4 – continued from previous page

URID	Title	Comment
UR002	Dynamic security testing of SkyFlok	The Dynamic testing modules are to be integrated in the following period
UR003	Continuous security assurance	The pilot is able to run the static analysis in its CI/CD pipeline allowing continuous security testing
UR004	Running the Static/Dynamic Analysis locally	Running the static analysis module locally is possible
UR005	Support Static Analysis for pilot's main programming languages	See UR001
UR006	Support Static Analysis for pilot's other programming languages	Support for Javascript and Typescript is not available yet
UR007	Running the toolkit for testing purposes	Both the static and dynamic testing modules have a DRY_RUN flag
UR008	Actionable security assessment	The results from the testing modules are not available on the Dashboard yet
UR009	Easy to understand security assessment	see UR008

5 Testing and demonstration

The testing procedure is the same for both pilot partners. The following list shows the high-level test targets for both pilots partners for the overall project in terms of integrations efforts. Note that local usage (e.g. on workstation PCs) of the modules is essential as this allows an easier adoption. The DRY_RUN feature is important to test and verify setups without actually publishing data.

Green points were successfully integrated and tested while orange still need integration efforts.

1. Login through Dashboard
2. Register a new Component
3. Run Static Analysis locally with DRY_RUN
4. Run Static Analysis in CI with DRY_RUN
5. Run Static Analysis in CI
6. Check Upload of SSCG in Dashboard
7. Run Dynamic Analysis locally with DRY_RUN
8. Run Dynamic Analysis in CI with DRY_RUN
9. Run Dynamic Analysis in CI
10. Check Upload of DSCG in the Dashboard
11. Check Generation of TBOM

Note that orange points are in many cases already touched by the pilot partners, a complete integration is missing though.

5.1 Common testing results

The integral part of the RESCALE solution is its Dashboard. This is where users interact with the platform. During the integration work pilot partners used the dashboard and tested its functionalities thoroughly. The Dashboard allows logging in using an account (see Figure 9), and then presents a list of components registered by the user as seen in Figure 11. A new component can also be created by supplying a name, programming language and a description as shown in Figure 10. Later a token to start the static code analysis can be generated. Pilot partners found the RESCALE Dashboard to be intuitive, and easy to use.

During the joint efforts of Tasks 5.1 and 5.2 a number of improvements for the dashboard were implemented based on feedback from pilot partners, like adding a version selector, search functionality and the ability to initiate the DSCG generation process from the producer view

as well, along with smaller visual, usability changes. This constant feedback loop will be maintained during the next phase of the project.

Figure 9: Logging into the dashboard

Figure 10: Registering a new component in the dashboard

Figure 11: Listing components in the dashboard

5.2 Testing results for pilot partner PST

As outlined in section 3.2 the static code analysis module was integrated into PST's GitHub CI System. The execution of an actual CI run can be seen in Figure 12. The output there is truncated to focus on the download of the static code analysis container and the actual execution of the module, specifically the tool SAVE-ME. After the tests are executed, an SSCG is generated and depending on the DRY_RUN variable the SSCG is published to the RESCALE platform.

In the last step the SSCG is also kept in a local cache such that developers are able to inspect it. In the last line a URL is provided to download the SSCG. An example SSCG can also be viewed in the [RESCALE SharePoint](#) [13], and a video demonstration of the process can be found on the [RESCALE YouTube channel](#) [5].

```
131 Status: Downloaded newer image for harbor.rescale-project.eu/wp3/static_analysis_module:latest
132 Validating sbom.json...
133 BOM validated successfully.
134 [Erlang] Processing Erlang source at /user_files/src/ with output at /app/out/test-reports/
135 [SAVE-ME] Running scan...
136 [SAVE-ME] Scan completed
137 [Erlang] Erlang source scans completed
138 [SSCG Generator] Generating SSCG...
139   - SBOM Path: /user_files/sbom.json
140   - Test Report Folder: /app/out/test-reports/
141   - SSCG Path: /app/out/sscg.json
142 JSON successfully stored to /app/out/sscg.json
143
144 Validating sscg.json...
145 BOM validated successfully.
146 [SSCG Generator] Publishing SSCG...
147   - SBOM Path: /user_files/sbom.json
148   - SSCG Path: /app/out/sscg.json
149 Request successfully sent.
150
151 SSCG generation/publishing process completed.
```

✓ Archive SSCG

```
1 ▶ Run actions/upload-artifact@v4
14 With the provided path, there will be 1 file uploaded
15 Artifact name is valid!
16 Root directory input is valid!
17 Beginning upload of artifact content to blob storage
18 Uploaded bytes 6380
19 Finished uploading artifact content to blob storage!
20 SHA256 hash of uploaded artifact zip is 57644722871de5b2f7b006573c42ed8e54ae0b3d0578c29cf8e0b066557fe8080
21 Finalizing artifact upload
22 Artifact SSCG.zip successfully finalized. Artifact ID 2584364058
23 Artifact SSCG has been successfully uploaded! Final size is 6380 bytes. Artifact ID is 2584364058
24 Artifact download URL: https://github.com/stritzinger/seawater/actions/runs/13281691804/artifacts/2584364058
```

Figure 12: Detailed View on the Job Execution for the Static Code Analysis Module

5.3 Testing results for pilot partner CC

Sections 4.2.2 and 4.3.2 describe how it was integrated into pilot partner CC's development pipeline. It is possible to run the static analysis both locally and in Bitbucket Pipelines with DRY_RUN or without it and uploading the SSCG to the RESCALE platform as seen in figure 13. A video demonstrating how pilot partner Chocolate Cloud deployed the RESCALE solution into its software pipeline can be found on the [RESCALE YouTube channel](#) [4].

Figure 13: Successfully running the Static Analyzer Module in Bitbucket Pipelines with up-loading the SSCG.

Running the Static Analyzer Module found the following issues in the tested code components. No real errors were identified at this phase of the project that would require attention. The outputs of the static analysis runs can be found on the [RESCALE SharePoint](#) [13].

- Rlnclib
 - 19 Notes: E.g. buffer/memcpy: Does not check for buffer overflows when copying to destination (CWE-120)
 - 3 Warnings: random/srand: This function is not sufficiently random for security-related functions such as key and nonce creation (CWE-327). These warnings were all found in test codes, so can be classified as False positives.
- Skyflok Email Service (excerpt)
 - 47 Low, E.g. Use of assert detected. The enclosed code will be removed when compiling to optimised byte code. Found in test codes, so can be classified as False positive.
 - 3 Medium: E.g. Possible SQL injection vector through string-based query construction. Classified as false positive because it is constructed using constants.

5.4 Key Performance Indicators

During the work carried out in Task 5.2 a number of KPIs were identified as possibly related to the pilot deployment activities. Details on how these KPIs relate to the pilots and some possible means of verification for some of these are presented in Table 5. Note that this list can change as the project progresses. A more detailed, exhaustive catalog and results will be presented in Task 5.3 and its deliverables.

Table 5: List of KPIs related to the Pilot deployment activities

KPI id	Title	Relevance to the piloting activities
KPI2.2	Detect more than 90% of known vulnerabilities at hardware and software level for the pilot's vulnerable hardware and software solutions	The hardware and software components of the pilot partners will be tested using both known benchmark applications and RESCALE solutions, then these results will be compared.
KPI4.1	At least two (2) use cases examined on the pilot trials	The two pilot partners present two different use cases which show the effectiveness of the RESCALE solution and its applicability on a wide range of scenarios.
KPI4.2	Achieve an adoption rate of 20% for the RESCALE platform by relevant stakeholders circles	In this iteration of testing, pilots were focused on integrating RESCALE solution into their environment. However, in the future, a comprehensive survey will be conducted to evaluate the adoption and usability of the proposed solution.
KPI4.3	Detection of more than 95% of total insecure components during piloting activities for known benchmark applications	see KPI2.2
KPI4.4	Construction of an informative mechanism for both security and non-security experts	Only a small number of developers at the pilot partners are experts in security. That's why the results of the tests and possible mitigation actions should be easy to understand and act upon.
iKPI1	Increased trust and acceptance of the blockchain-assisted management processes of TBOM updates by collaborating parties in supply chains by at least 30%, including at least two hardware and two software components.	see KPI4.2
iKPI4	Alignment of the RESCALE approach with the new NIS directive for security assessment and validation of the RESCALE overall security testing framework, integrating both static and dynamic security and privacy properties, in at least two industry-led pilot scenarios.	NIS Directive and its updated version NIS2 defines security requirements which needs to be satisfied and RESCALE solution will help pilots to perform security audits and assessments. Those reports may serve as evidence of security implementation and risk mitigation.

Table 5 – continued from previous page

KPI id	Title	Relevance to the piloting activities
iKPI7	Identify at least 95% of insecure mechanisms for accessing and processing sensitive data at the piloting activities for known benchmark applications.	see KPI2.2
iKPI8	Increase in self-assessed preparedness levels of TBOM components at the piloting phase by at least 50%.	Detailed pilot reports will be produced that document the improvements in supply chain security and preparedness levels as a result of using TBOM components.
iKPI15	Achieve more than 95% resilience on cyberattacks and on non-malicious failures during the project piloting activities on known benchmark applications.	see KPI2.2
iKPI16	Increase the perception of security through the use of TBOM and Trustor by 20%.	see iKPI8
iKPI17	Reduce time to detect known and emerging vulnerabilities in supply chains by 10%.	Currently it takes a long time and manual effort to detect new vulnerabilities in the pilot partner's development activities. With the help of the Security Assurance components this can be greatly improved.
iKPI27	At least 80% acceptance of proposed technologies that are piloted in two different environments.	see KPI4.2

6 Roadmap to Final Version

6.1 Next Steps for Dynamic Testing Integration

As explained in previous sections, it is still necessary to integrate the dynamic testing module for both pilot partners. This will require a more complex automation setup due to the higher complexity of that module compared to the static code analysis module. A first integration is expected to be finished within the next three months after this report is submitted. There were already successful attempts to generate a DSCG and even a TBOM using manually crafted development setups.

6.2 Expanding Testing Scope for More Components

For demonstrating how real supply chains can utilize the RESCALE platform, the pilot partners will work with more components and their dependencies such that more data (SSCG, DSCG, TBOM) is generated. For the pilot partners it is of high relevance how real, complex supply chains are handled by the platform.

Another major point is the trust assurance of the generated and published data. The pilot partners are expected to integrate security mechanisms that will enable trust in generated documents and the ability to trace down ill-generated (corrupted, manipulated etc.) data. The foundation for these mechanisms is currently subject to project research in WP4.

In addition, the integration of more tools (see figures 1 and 2) and their refinement represents a large body of work for the pilot partners. Note that many tools require a very specific configuration and additional specifications on how to test a specific piece of software or hardware. Also, as of now, only a smaller part of the WP3 tools is integrated into their respective module and probably all of them will benefit from direct feedback to the tools developer when used on real world setups.

6.3 Enhancements in BOM Tooling

Besides the integration of RESCALE specific tooling, the pilot partners are also striving to enhance BOM related tooling. From the perspective of an industrial end user, it is obvious that major parts of the open source landscape regarding BOM processing are under-developed. Possible enhancements lie particular in the generation of SBOMs where, at least in the case of the Erlang programming language, the technological foundation lacks major features and/or sophistication.

6.4 On-Premises Deployments

Another topic of less importance is a possible installation on-premises of the RESCALE platform. As of now, the platform is deployed using specific (cloud) technologies within the in-

frastructure of a partner. For an on-premises setup, it is desirable to enable the pilot partners to install the platform as easily as possible.

7 Conclusion

The first iteration of the pilot deployment and integration shows how RESCALE established a robust foundation for securing the supply chain through the Static Analysis module. This initial integration played a crucial role in improving the module by uncovering and resolving numerous bugs, ultimately enhancing its effectiveness. The insights gained from this process will significantly contribute to the project's ongoing development, ensuring continuous refinement and optimization.

While the Static Analysis module has been successfully integrated, the main challenge ahead is incorporating the Dynamic Testing module. This next step will be essential in strengthening the overall security framework in the pilots, as it will complement static analysis with real-time assessment capabilities that include runtime vulnerabilities, API fuzzing, memory safety and other areas. The experience gained from the initial deployment as running the modules locally and in CI/CD pipelines will help streamline this integration, making it a key focus for future iterations.

As the first version of this deliverable, this document outlines the foundational work achieved so far. The next iteration will focus on the integration of the Dynamic Testing module, which will complete the security validation process as well as incorporating the newly developed features of the RESCALE platform such as the trust mechanisms described in WP4. As development continues, ongoing refinements will further enhance the RESCALE project's ability to secure the supply chain.

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